

RADX-UP Bibliometrics Report

Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics in
Underserved Populations: Bibliometrics
Report

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Table of Contents

Table of Tables	3
Table of Figures	4
Abbreviations	5
Executive Summary	6
Background	6
Methods	6
Results	6
Conclusion	11
Background	11
RADx-UP Evaluation	11
RADx-UP Evaluation Questions Aligned with Bibliometric Analysis	12
Bibliometrics	12
Methods	12
Project Demographics	12
Data Sample	16
Data Tools	16
Scopus	16
iCite	16
Bibliometric Measures	16
Process	19
Data Analysis & Visualization	19
Results	19
Publication Count	19
Citation Impact	25
Scopus Citation Counts	25
PlumX Metrics	27
Discussion & Conclusions	28
Recommendations & Implications	29
Limitations	30
Next Steps	30

Table of Tables

Table 1: Overview of Bibliometric Measures	16
Table 2: RADx-UP publication count by top sources in Scopus (as of March 31, 2023). This includes sources publishing 4 or more of the 189 RADx-UP publications indexed in Scopus	24
Table 3: Relative Citation Ratio Data (as of March 31, 2023).....	27

Table of Figures

Figure 1: RADx-UP Project and Supplement count, RADx-UP publication count, and RADx-UP citation count by target population (as of March 31, 2023).....	8
Figure 2: Relative Citation Ratio Distribution, Mean, and Median for RADx-UP publications (as of March 31, 2023).....	9
Figure 3: RADx-UP publication count (sources: Scopus and PubMed) and citation count (source: Scopus) by TSBM testing benefits (as of March 31, 2023).....	10
Figure 4: RADx-UP Publication altmetric counts with PlumX Metrics (as of March 31, 2023).....	10
Figure 5: RADx-UP Projects and Supplements from Phase I, Phase II, and Phase III by grant start date (as of March 31, 2023).....	13
Figure 6: RADx-UP Project and Supplement count by population (as of March 31, 2023).....	14
Figure 7: RADx-UP Project and Supplement count by region of the United States (as of March 31, 2023).....	14
Figure 8: RADx-UP Project count by awardee minority-serving institution type (as of March 31, 2023). ..	15
Figure 9: RADx-UP publication count by year (as of March 31, 2023).....	20
Figure 10: RADx-UP publication count by Scopus publication type (as of March 31, 2023).....	20
Figure 11: RADx-UP publication count by quantitative methodology (as of March 31, 2023).....	21
Figure 12: RADx-UP publication count (source: Scopus and PubMed) and citation count (source: Scopus) by community outreach strategy (as of March 31, 2023).....	22
Figure 13: RADx-UP publication count by U.S. Region (as of March 31, 2023).....	23
Figure 14: RADx-UP publication count (sources: Scopus and PubMed) and citation count (source: Scopus) by TSBM vaccination benefits (as of March 31, 2023).....	24
Figure 15: RADx-UP publication citations in Scopus by year (as of March 31, 2023).....	25
Figure 16: RADx-UP publication citations in Scopus by methodology (as of March 31, 2023).....	26
Figure 17: Citations per RADx-UP publication in Scopus by U.S. region (as of March 31, 2023).....	26

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interfaces
CB	Citation Benchmarking
CDCC	Coordination and Data Collection Center
DOI	Digital object identifier
EO	Evaluation objective
FWCI	Field-Weighted Citation Impact
NIH	National Institutes of Health
NoA	Notice of Award
PMID	PubMed unique identifier
RADx-UP	Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations
RCR	Relative Citation Ratio
T&E	Tracking & Evaluation
TSBM	Translational Science Benefits Model
UNC	University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Executive Summary

Background

The National Institutes of Health (NIH) supports the Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program that aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19 associated morbidity and mortality. One of the evaluation objectives of the RADx-UP Program is to measure its research and program productivity in advancing critical knowledge on reducing COVID-19 morbidity and mortality through community-engaged testing. To achieve this objective, the RADx-UP Tracking and Evaluation team used bibliometrics analytical methods to quantitatively assess the scientific impacts of RADx-UP publication and citation data. This analysis, in conjunction with complementary evaluation methods of peer-reviewed publications, helps to identify how RADx-UP improves understanding of COVID-19 testing in scientific communities.

Methods

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team sources for RADx-UP scholarly publications through (1) Scopus and PubMed using automated searches of RADx-UP Project grant numbers and (2) Quarterly surveys to RADx-UP Project staff. The data collection period spanned from September 26, 2020, to March 31, 2023. As of this analysis's cutoff date (March 31, 2023), we identified a total of 196 publication citations related to RADx-UP. Notably, 189 of these citations were available in Scopus, and 194 were accessible in PubMed. PlumX Metrics, integrated within Scopus, provided alternative metrics that gauge the types and levels of engagement with RADx-UP publications, such as reader count and policy citations. Of the 196 RADx-UP citations, 194 were available for alternative metrics analysis via PlumX Metrics. In addition to these data sources, we harnessed the capabilities of iCite, a web application hosted by the NIH Office of Portfolio Analysis. iCite offered a dashboard of bibliometric information for RADx-UP publications, including the calculation of Relative Citation Ratios (RCRs).

Our bibliometric measures include RCR, research productivity, publication by source title, and citation impact. RCRs were chosen as a key indicator due to their capacity to compare NIH-funded publications with peer NIH publications. Additionally, PlumX Metrics were employed to capture altmetrics, which provide insights into the translation of research beyond scientific literature. Using publication-level data from the RADx-UP Tracking & Evaluation Content Analysis, we compared the project count, the publication count, and the citation count for RADx-UP target populations, U.S. regions, minority-serving institution types, study approaches, community outreach strategies, and testing and vaccination topics. All measures were analyzed and visualized using Microsoft Excel and R.

Results

At the time of our analysis, there were a total of 137 NIH-supported RADx-UP Projects, distributed across three phases: Phase I, Phase II, and Phase III. Aggregate data demonstrated that these projects have a broad reach, encompassing all underserved target populations and regions within the United States. Some projects serve multiple COVID-19 target populations or span multiple U.S. regions. Geographically, publications were concentrated in the Southeast (47) and the West (33).

In 2022, RADx-UP Projects witnessed a significant surge in scholarly productivity, with 119 new publications, marking a notable increase compared to 2021. However, it's important to note that our data collection for 2023 remains incomplete as it halted at the end of the first quarter. Publications

from 2023 are on pace to approximate 2022 output by the end of the year. Out of the 196 total publications, 168 were research articles and many of the articles utilized observational research design (92 publications and 498 citations). RADx-UP projects (66 out of 196 publications) substantially utilized partnerships with community-based organizations as a dominant community outreach or engagement strategy during research design and implementation.

Among the vulnerable populations served, Hispanic/Latino populations (98 projects), Black/African American populations (90 projects), and older adults (58 projects) featured prominently (**Figure 1**). The top 3 publications were focused on the following populations: Hispanic/Latino (46), Black African American (31) and Children/adolescents (26). RADx-UP publications were significantly cited in the literature. The top 3 target population with the most cited articles include older adults (276), Hispanic/Latino (205) and Black African American (171). Despite representing a smaller proportion of funded projects and publications, older adults garnered the most citations (276) compared to other populations. The publication with the most citations (61) as of March 31, 2023, is “Lessons learned from frontline skilled nursing facility staff regarding COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy”, which describes vaccine hesitancy expressed in 26 town hall meetings from 193 staff across 50 skilled nursing facilities.

RADx-UP Project Count, Publication Count, and Citation Count by Population

Figure 1: RADx-UP Project and Supplement count, RADx-UP publication count, and RADx-UP citation count by target population (as of March 31, 2023). Please note that publications in our dataset also come from the RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center, Community Collaboration Grant Program, Say YES! COVID Test, and You and Me COVID Free, which are not represented in this figure. We also count parent projects and supplement projects separately. These project counts may not match official project counts available on the RADx-UP.org website, which counts projects and supplements together. Projects and supplements are sometimes published separately, which leads us to think of them as separate in bibliometric analysis.

RADx-UP publications have a strong research influence in the COVID-19 literature. Scholarly publication output displayed a clear upward trend, and citation counts indicated substantial research influence. The 189 articles (from Scopus) had a combined total of 966 citations. Thirteen articles published in 2021 had received 20 or more citation each. Four of these articles (Berry et al., 2021; Carlsten et al., 2021; Harrison et al., 2021; and Klonoff et al., 2021;) had received 40 or more citations each, indicating significant influence in the research community. In addition, Research influence as measured by time- and field- normalized RCR scores indicate the RADx-UP publications have a greater-than-typical citation rate compared to NIH-funded papers in the same field and year (Figure 2). This in turn, indicates greater-than-typical scientific influence of these publications, compared to that benchmark group of papers. These RCR scores continue to show strong uptake of RADx-UP publications in scholarly communities, improving our understanding of COVID-19 testing and vaccination among underserved populations.

Relative Citation Ratio (RCR) with Mean and Median for RADx-UP Publications
(N=194 Publications; 65 with RCRs)

Figure 2: Relative Citation Ratio Distribution, Mean, and Median for RADx-UP publications (as of March 31, 2023)

In terms of benefits from the Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM), the most substantial gains were observed in the community & public health category, aligning with the RADx-UP program's mission. Testing benefits predominantly revolved around testing delivery and uptake, followed closely by testing accessibility, community testing services, and public health testing practices (**Figure 3**). Many publications reported multiple translational testing benefits. Altmetric data like mentions and citations in news, social media, and policy also indicate that RADx-UP findings are translating beyond scholarly communities (**Figure 4**). PlumX altmetric data highlighted substantial public engagement, particularly through policy citations, signifying the program's societal impact and relevance to policymakers and advocacy groups.

RADx-UP Publication Count and Citation Count by TSBM Testing Benefits

Figure 3: RADx-UP publication count (sources: Scopus and PubMed) and citation count (source: Scopus) by TSBM testing benefits (as of March 31, 2023)

Total Metric Counts for 194 RADx-UP Publications with PlumX Metrics

Figure 4: RADx-UP Publication altmetric counts with PlumX Metrics (as of March 31, 2023)

Combining publication content analysis data with bibliometric data shows that RADx-UP publications are improving the understanding of testing and vaccination in most target populations funded through the grant. Policy citations demonstrate that the social, ethical, and behavioral implications of COVID-19 testing and vaccination from the RADx-UP Program are relevant for government decision-making.

Conclusion

In this second year of bibliometrics reporting, the RCR scores continue to show strong uptake of RADx-UP publications in scholarly communities, improving our understanding of COVID-19 testing and vaccination among underserved populations. Altmetric data like mentions and citations in news, social media, and policy also indicate that RADx-UP findings are translating beyond scholarly communities. However, there is still a need to publish data on less represented target population and demonstrate the cost-effectiveness as well as the policy impacts of COVID-19 testing and vaccination interventions.

Background

RADx-UP Evaluation

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics for Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19 associated morbidity and mortality.

The program seeks to achieve this primary aim through:

- Understanding and alleviating barriers to testing across the nation.
- Utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of FDA-authorized/approved diagnostics among vulnerable populations in underserved geographic locations.
- Strengthening the available data on disparities in infection rates; disease progression and outcomes; differences in testing access and uptake patterns; and identifying strategies to address disparities in COVID-19 diagnostics.

The RADx-UP Program will enable a targeted public health response to COVID-19 and build evidence-based approaches to identify and address disparities in COVID-19 diagnostic testing uptake and effectiveness in underserved populations.

Bibliometrics analysis, in conjunction with complementary evaluation methods of peer-reviewed publications, can show how RADx-UP improves understanding of COVID-19 testing in scientific communities. Along with bibliometrics, the T&E team employs content analysis and network analysis to meet the above objectives.

RADx-UP Evaluation Questions Aligned with Bibliometric Analysis

1. To what extent are RADx-UP projects contributing to increasing the knowledge and understanding of the **social, ethical and behavioral implications of COVID-19 testing** and vaccination among underserved populations?
2. What are the research productivity impacts of RADx-UP in **advancing knowledge on COVID-19 testing resource and behaviors** including the **importance of community-led initiatives** in reducing COVID-19 mortality and morbidity disparities?

Bibliometrics

Bibliometrics involves the use of quantitative analysis methods to examine different aspects of bibliometric data such as publication and citation data. It is especially useful for analyzing large publication data sets that cannot reasonably be reviewed manually (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2018) (Donthu, Kumar, Mukherjee, Pandey, & Lim, 2021). Bibliometric analysis is one approach used to analyze and measure the impact of research. Bibliometric indicators, such as publication counts and citation counts, are interpreted as indicators, though not direct measures, of research productivity and research impact or influence, respectively (Waltman & Noyons, 2018) (Donthu, Kumar, Mukherjee, Pandey, & Lim, 2021).

Bibliometric analyses tend to have either a descriptive or an evaluative purpose or scope. Evaluative analyses such as this one focus on the contributions of research entities and help ascertain research performance (i.e., output, influence, and collaboration patterns) of that research entity. Examples include an individual researcher's productivity, an institutional unit's research impact, or a funding award's research return on investment (Cabezas-Clavijo & Torres-Salinas, 2021) (Moral-Muñoz, Herrera-Viedma, Santisteban-Espejo, & Cobo, 2020) (Donthu, Kumar, Mukherjee, Pandey, & Lim, 2021).

The purpose of this report is to present the current (as of March 31, 2023) research productivity and the impact or influence of the publications from the 137 RADx-UP funded research as measured through bibliometric analysis.

Methods

Project Demographics

RADx-UP Projects Funding Cycle Characteristics. At the time of this analysis, there are 137 NIH-supported RADx-UP Projects, funded in three phases: Phase I, II, and III. See **Figure 5** below for counts of projects by RADx-UP grant start dates.

RADx-UP Project Grant Start Date (N = 137 Projects)

Figure 5: RADx-UP Projects and Supplements from Phase I, Phase II, and Phase III by grant start date (as of March 31, 2023). Please note that publications in our dataset also come from the RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center, Community Collaboration Grant Program, Say YES! COVID Test, and You and Me COVID Free, which are not represented in this figure. We also count parent projects and supplement projects separately. These project counts may not match official project counts available on the RADx-UP.org website, which counts projects and supplements together. Projects and supplements are sometimes published separately, which leads us to think of them as separate in bibliometric analysis.

COVID-19 Target Populations Served by and Geographic Reach of RADx-UP Projects. In aggregate, RADx-UP Projects reach all underserved target populations and regions of the US. Some projects serve multiple COVID-19 target populations (**Figure 6**) or more than one region of the US (**Figure 7**). Across projects, the most common vulnerable populations served are Hispanic/Latino populations (98), Black/African American populations (90), and older adults (58). RADx-UP Projects are geographically distributed across the country, with the plurality of projects located in the US Southeast and West regions (**Figure 7**).

RADx-UP Project Count by Population (N = 137 Projects)

Figure 6: RADx-UP Project and Supplement count by population (as of March 31, 2023). Please note that publications in our dataset also come from the RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center, Community Collaboration Grant Program, Say YES! COVID Test, and You and Me COVID Free, which are not represented in this figure. We also count parent projects and supplement projects separately. These project counts may not match official project counts available on the RADx-UP.org website, which counts projects and supplements together. Projects and supplements are sometimes published separately, which leads us to think of them as separate in bibliometric analysis.

RADx-UP Project Count by U.S. Region (N = 137 Projects)

Figure 7: RADx-UP Project and Supplement count by region of the United States (as of March 31, 2023). Please note that publications in our dataset also come from the RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center, Community Collaboration Grant Program, Say YES! COVID Test, and You and Me COVID Free, which are not represented in this figure. We also count parent projects and supplement projects separately. These project counts may not match official project counts available on the RADx-UP.org website, which counts projects and supplements together. Projects and supplements are sometimes published separately, which leads us to think of them as separate in bibliometric analysis.

Minority-Serving Institution (MSI) Representation among RADx-UP Projects. The NIH awarded some RADx-UP Projects to four key types of minority-serving institutions. Across projects, the most common designations are Asian American and Native American Pacific Islanders-serving (13), Hispanic-serving (11), Historically Black College or University (4), and Tribally Controlled institutions (1) (National Center for Education Statistics, 2021). The remaining projects are not minority-serving institutions from these four main categories. **Figure 8** below shows project count by the type of minority-serving institution.¹

RADx-UP Project Count by Minority-Serving Institution (N = 137 Projects)

Figure 8: RADx-UP Project count by awardee minority-serving institution type (as of March 31, 2023). Publications in our dataset also come from the RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center, Community Collaboration Grant Program, Say YES! COVID Test, and You and Me COVID Free, which are not represented in this figure. We also count parent projects and supplement projects separately. These project counts may not match official project counts available on the RADx-UP.org website, which counts projects and supplements together. Projects and supplements are sometimes published separately, which leads us to think of them as separate in bibliometric analysis.

¹ We rely on the United States Department of Education to categorize awardee institutions according to four categories of minority-serving institution: Asian American and Native American Pacific Islander-serving institution, Hispanic-serving institution, Historically Black College or University, and Tribally Controlled institution. The Department of Education determines Asian American and Native American Pacific Islander-serving institution and Hispanic-serving institution status through undergraduate demographic targets, which means that if an institution’s proportion of Hispanic or Asian American students varies significantly from year-to-year, the status of the institution could change (Higher Education Act, 1965). The Department of Education designates an institution a Historically Black College or University if that institution “was established prior to 1964, whose principal mission was, and is, the education of [B]lack Americans” (U.S. Department of Education, n.d.). The Department of Education recognizes the designation of Tribally Controlled institutions through the American Indian Higher Education Consortium (U.S. Department of Education, n.d.).

Data Sample

We find RADx-UP scholarly publications through (1) Scopus and PubMed using automated searches of RADx-UP Project grant numbers and (2) Quarterly surveys to RADx-UP Project staff. From September 26, 2020, through March 31, 2023, we identified 196 total publication citations. At this data collection point for the 2023 analysis, 189 of 196 were available in Scopus and so included in citation count analysis. Out of 196 RADx-UP citations, 194 were available in PubMed and so could be included in Relative Citation Ratio analysis using iCite.

Data Tools

Scopus

Scopus is a subscription-based Elsevier research intelligence product. Specifically, it is a database of peer-reviewed literature that tracks citations. Citation counts are retrievable in Scopus citation exports or document records. As of March 31, 2023, 189 of the 196 RADx-UP citations were available in Scopus and could be included in the citation count analysis.

Through its integration of PlumX Metrics, Scopus also provides alternative metrics indicating types and levels of engagement, such as reader count and policy citations, with Scopus-indexed publications. PlumX Metrics data are accessible via a Scopus API. The **Bibliometric Measures** section includes additional information about PlumX Metrics. As of March 31, 2023, 194 of the 196 RADx-UP citations were available in PlumX Metrics for alternative metrics analysis.

iCite

iCite is a web application hosted by the NIH Office of Portfolio Analysis that provides a dashboard of bibliometric information for journal publications within a defined analysis group provided to the tool for analysis (e.g., the set of 194 of 196 total RADx-UP publications) (Hutchins, Yuan, Anderson, & Santangelo, 2016). An analysis group can consist of one publication or a large group of publications. iCite allows a maximum of 10,000 PMIDs at a time in queries and analyses (National Institutes of Health Office of Portfolio Analysis, n.d.). The iCite database currently contains PubMed article citations published from 1980 to present. As of March 31, 2023, 194 of the 196 RADx-UP citations were available in PubMed and so could be included in Relative Citation Ratio analysis by iCite.

Data from iCite can help further understand the scientific influence of the scholarly publications in the analysis group of publications; citations to a paper indicate influence. iCite uses the Relative Citation Ratio (RCR), a normalized citation score assigned to papers based on comparing the number of citations per year to NIH-funded papers published in the same field and year.

Bibliometric Measures

We used Scopus to obtain citation counts associated with the 189 RADx-UP citations indexed in Scopus as of March 31, 2023. We captured PlumX Metrics data on May 31, 2023, available for 194 RADx-UP citations based on a search on DOI. **Table 1** below presents an overview of bibliometric measures. We chose RCR as a key indicator of impact or influence because RADx-UP is an NIH-funded project, and the RCR specifically compares NIH-funded publications to peer NIH publications. We also chose to capture altmetrics with PlumX because altmetrics may indicate translation to other media beyond scientific literature.

Table 1: Overview of Bibliometric Measures

Bibliometric Measure	Metrics	Data Source	Analysis Tool
Research Productivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total number of publications in a calendar year • Total publications by institution type • Total publications by target population • Total publication by project type • Total publications by methodology 	Scopus, PubMed & manually curated dataset	Microsoft Excel
Publication by Document Type	Number of publications for each document type	Scopus, PubMed & manually curated dataset	Microsoft Excel
Publication by Source Title	Top publishing journals of the included publications	Scopus, PubMed & manually curated dataset	Microsoft Excel
Citation Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total citation counts • Citation counts by institution type, target population, project type, methodology. • Citations per publication • Relative Citation Ratio (RCR) 	Scopus, PubMed & iCite	Microsoft Excel
PlumX Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Captures • Citations • Mentions • Social Media • Usage 	PlumX via Scopus (API)	Microsoft Excel

Research Productivity: The total count of RADx-UP publications published in the calendar year that T&E analysts determined to be COVID-related.

Publication by Source Title: The count of RADx-UP scholarly publications categorized by the journal titles that published the papers. We included journal titles publishing two or more RADx-UP publications in visualizations.

Citation Impact: The accrual of citations by papers is an indicator of scientific influence. Citations take time to accrue, and the cumulative citation count will typically increase over the months and years after publication.

Total Citation Count: The total citation count shows how many times this publication has been cited in other scholarly publications indexed in the same database, in this case, Scopus.

Citations Per Publication: Citations per publication indicate the average citation impact of each set of publications. Dividing the total citation count by the number of publications in the analysis set yields the citations per publication.

$$\text{Citations per publication} = \frac{\text{total citation count}}{\text{total publications in the analysis group}}$$

Outlying publications in a small data set and excessive self-citation can artificially inflate this average value. Following on last year's pilot analysis, this year RADx-UP publications have had another year for citations to accrue. This metric should also be used with care in assessing the performance of publications in the early stages of a new research effort or authored by early-career researchers (Elsevier, 2019). As more time passes, the cumulative citation count across RADx-UP publications will continue to increase.

Relative Citation Ratio (RCR): The RCR metric developed by the NIH Office of Portfolio Analysis represents a citation-based measure of scientific influence of one or more scholarly publications. The NIH Office of Portfolio Analysis defines RCR as the citations per year of each paper, compared to the citations per year received by NIH-funded papers in the same field and year (Hutchins, Yuan, Anderson, & Santangelo, 2016).

$$\text{Relative Citation Ratio} = \frac{\text{a paper's average number of citations per year}}{\text{citation rate of NIH funded papers in the same field and year}}$$

A paper with an RCR of 1.0 has received the same number of citations per year as the typical (median) NIH-funded paper in its field. RCR values greater than 1.0 indicate greater citations per year than the median NIH-funded paper in its field. For the RCR calculation, the co-citation network, which includes all the publications cited alongside the scholarly publications, defines the field for each scholarly publication. Developers of the RCR metric argue that a scholarly publications' co-citation network more flexibly and precisely represents the interdisciplinary nature of biomedical and health sciences research than traditional bibliometric categories like "biology and biochemistry" or "molecular biology." The displayed RCR values are the maximum (MAX), the average (MEAN), the standard error of the mean (SEM), and the median (MED) of the papers in the analyzed group (National Institutes of Health Office of Portfolio Analysis, n.d.).

PlumX Metrics (Plum Analytics altmetrics): In the PlumX system, Plum Analytics collects indicators of people's interactions with individual research outputs and categorizes them in the five categories described below to enable comparisons of similar interaction types across these outputs (Plum Analytics, n.d.). These "alternative metrics" or indicators tend to accrue substantially faster than citations and can provide early indicators of engagement with research outputs.

- **Captures** – This metric indicates that someone wants to come back to a paper or other work. Captures can be a leading indicator of future citations. Examples include bookmarks, code forks, favorites, followers, readers, watchers, exports/saves and subscribers.
- **Citations** - This category contains citations from both traditional citation indexes such as Scopus, as well as citations that help indicate societal impact such as citations by clinical or policy

documents. Examples include citation indexes, patent citations, clinical citations, and policy citations.

- **Mentions** – This category measures activities such as news articles or blog posts about research. Mentions are an indicator that people are engaging with the research. Examples include blog mentions, comments, news media mentions, reviews, and Wikipedia references.
- **Social Media** - This category includes tweets, Facebook likes, etc. that reference the research. Social Media can help measure “buzz” and attention research is receiving. Social media can also be a good measure of the promotion of a particular piece of research. Examples include comments, tweets, shares, likes, ratings, and recommendations.
- **Usage** - This category includes indicators that suggest people are reading a scholarly publication or otherwise using a research output. Examples include abstract views, clicks, downloads, full text views, library holdings, and video plays. According to Plum Analytics the Usage category that researchers want to know after citations (Plum Analytics, n.d.).

Process

Automated search alerts were set up in Scopus and PubMed. These recurring searches query the funding fields for RADx-UP Project numbers or keywords. For this initial bibliometric analysis, we selected a publication collection cutoff date (March 31, 2023) at which time we had collected 196 total RADx-UP publications on the topic of COVID-19. As of March 31, 2023, Scopus indexed 189 of the 196 total RADx-UP scholarly publications. We exported final citation data for analysis, including citation counts, from Scopus on this date. As of March 31, 2023, PubMed indexed 194 of the 196 total RADx-UP publications. We imported the 194 PubMed unique identifiers (PMIDs) to NIH iCite. A PMID is the unique identifier number used in PubMed for each scholarly publication. We downloaded iCite generated citation statistics as of the cutoff date, including NIH RCRs, for further analysis. We used Excel to clean and standardize the Scopus and PubMed citation data and to produce charts. Also on March 31, 2023, we queried PlumX Metrics data using the Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) of the 196 total RADx-UP publications and exported PlumX Metrics data for the 194 publications via the Scopus PlumX API.

Data Analysis & Visualization

We analyzed and visualized data exported from Scopus and iCite using Microsoft Excel and R for this bibliometric analysis.

Results

Publication Count

Overall, 2022 was a much more productive year for publications than 2021, with 119 new publications from RADx-UP projects (**Figure 9**). Since data collection stopped at the end of the first quarter, the publication count for 2023 is incomplete.

RADx-UP Publication Count by Year (N = 189)

Figure 9: RADx-UP publication count by year (as of March 31, 2023). Data source: Scopus

According to Scopus' document type classification system, the vast majority (168) of RADx-UP publications are original research articles, and the second most common type is review (8) (Figure 10). Editorials, notes, and letters comprise the remaining 13 publications.

RADx-UP Publications by Document Type (N = 189 Publications)

Figure 10: RADx-UP publication count by Scopus publication type (as of March 31, 2023). Data source: Scopus

Out of 196 RADx-UP publications, 135 utilized a quantitative data collection and analysis approach. Observational study design (92 out of 135) is the most common quantitative method employed across publications (Figure 11). While experimental and evaluation studies may lead to more rigorous intervention development and testing, observational studies can help to define the problem of health inequity and possibly show the benefits of existing interventions. Publications may have more than one quantitative method. For example, a single paper may report on multiple study aims, like an observational aim and a cost-benefit aim.

RADx-UP Publication Count by Quantitative Method (N = 196 Publications)

Figure 11: RADx-UP publication count by quantitative methodology (as of March 31, 2023)

All 196 RADx-UP publications were analyzed through content analysis to assess their community engagement strategy. A total of 94 out of 196 publications used at least one community engagement strategy (**Figure 12**). The most common engagement strategy indicated in RADx-UP publications is partnerships with community-based organizations (CBOs; 66), followed by focus groups and/or surveys (39). Publications may indicate more than one community outreach strategy. For example, a RADx-UP project may use print media, social media, and community events to communicate the importance of regular COVID-19 testing.

RADx-UP Publication Count and Citation Count by Community Outreach Strategy

Figure 12: RADx-UP publication count (source: Scopus and PubMed) and citation count (source: Scopus) by community outreach strategy (as of March 31, 2023)

Examining the target population focused on across RADx-UP publications revealed that the target population indicated in the publications match the target population proposed by the RADx-UP projects in their research plans. The most publications have been written about Hispanic/Latino populations (46) and the second most publications are about Black/African American populations (31) (Figure 1).

From the publication dataset so far, we have seen the most publications on populations in the Southeast (47) and the West (33) (Figure 13). Not illustrated here, no publications have yet covered populations in U.S. territories. Some original research using national data and some publication types like editorials, letters, and reviews are not associated with any region, so the results do not sum to 196.

RADx-UP Publication Count by U.S. Region (N = 146 Publications)

Figure 13: RADx-UP publication count by U.S. Region (as of March 31, 2023)

We used the constructs from the Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) to categorize all 196 RADx-UP publications by testing and vaccination topics through content analysis. Translational science benefits largely accrued in the community & public health category, in keeping with the mission and expectations of the RADx-UP program (**Figure 3**). The greatest number of testing benefits documented in scholarly publications were those related to testing delivery and uptake, followed closely by testing accessibility, community testing services, and public health testing practices. A publication may have more than one translational testing benefit. For example, a research project may document both findings on where to place test centers (public health testing practices) and communication strategies for advertising those test centers (testing delivery and uptake).

Like testing translational benefits, vaccination translational benefits are primarily in the community and public health category. The greatest number of vaccination benefits are in vaccine hesitancy (37) and vaccine delivery & uptake (30) (**Figure 14**). There are fewer overall vaccination benefits than testing benefits documented, which fits the grant mission of primarily reducing COVID-19 testing inequity. As in testing translational benefits, a publication may document more than one vaccination translational benefit.

RADx-UP Publication Count and Citation Count by TSBM Vaccination Benefits

Figure 14: RADx-UP publication count (sources: Scopus and PubMed) and citation count (source: Scopus) by TSBM vaccination benefits (as of March 31, 2023)

The American Journal of Public Health (23) and Pediatrics (17) contain the largest and second largest quantity of journal articles from RADx-UP (Table 2). Both have hosted special supplements or issues that focus on RADx-UP projects.

Table 2: RADx-UP publication count by top sources in Scopus (as of March 31, 2023). This includes sources publishing 4 or more of the 189 RADx-UP publications indexed in Scopus

Source Title	Publications
American Journal of Public Health	23
Pediatrics	17
BMC Public Health	9
Drug And Alcohol Dependence	8
Vaccines	7
Journal of Racial and Ethnic Health Disparities	6
Journal of the American Geriatrics Society	6
PLOS One	6
International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	4
JAMA Network Open	4

Journal of School Health	4
Journal of the American Medical Directors Association	4

Citation Impact

Scopus Citation Counts

Of the 196 total RADx-UP publications examined in this analysis, 189 of them were available for retrieval from Scopus. The citation overview in Scopus shows these 189 publications have accumulated.

- **966 citations** – self-citations *included* (as of 3/31/2023)
- **794 citations** – self-citations *excluded* (as of 3/31/2023)

Citation counts in Scopus are based on citing scholarly publications indexed in Scopus. Overall, 2022 saw a substantial rise in citations of RADx-UP literature (**Figure 15**). Additionally, if trends from the first quarter of 2023 continue, the total number of citations in 2023 will be a further increase.

Figure 15: RADx-UP publication citations in Scopus by year (as of March 31, 2023)

Among publications with a quantitative method or mixed method, publications with observational methods received by far the largest share of citations (498) (Figure 16). The share of observational citations is disproportionately greater than the share of observational publications, reflecting disproportionate citation of observational RADx-UP studies.

RADx-UP Citation Count by Quantitative Method (N = 189 Publications)

Figure 16: RADx-UP publication citations in Scopus by methodology (as of March 31, 2023)

RADx-UP citation counts by population largely reflect the publication counts by population with one notable exception: older adults (**Figure 1**). Though RADx-UP projects focused on older adults represent a lower share of RADx-UP funded projects and publications than other populations, they have 276 citations, more than any other population.

The Southeast region with the most RADx-UP projects (47) also has the most publications (47) and citations (165), with 3.51 citations per publication on average (**Figure 17**). However, projects in the West (41) have a relatively small number of publications (33) and citations (67) compared to other regions with less projects, with 2.03 citations per publication on average. Conversely, only 25 projects are in the Northeast, but they have the highest number of citations per publication (4.04), with 23 publications and 93 citations.

Citations per RADx-UP Publication by U.S. Region (N = 189 Publications)

Figure 17: Citations per RADx-UP publication in Scopus by U.S. region (as of March 31, 2023)

NIH iCite Relative Citation Ratio (RCR)

The NIH RCR is the main method for comparing the RADx-UP publications dataset with other NIH-funded projects. As of March 31, 2023, 194 of the 196 RADx-UP publications were available in PubMed and could be analyzed by iCite. **Of those 194 publications, 65 of these papers were assigned RCR values** as of March 31, 2023. The 65 publications assigned RCR values include one scholarly publication published in 2020, 44 scholarly publications published in 2021, and 20 of the 119 scholarly publications published in 2022 that had received five citations or more.²

The average (mean) RCR score for the 65 RADx-UP publications with RCRs is 3.17 (**Table 3; Figure 2**). This RCR value indicates that, on average, at the time of this analysis, these RADx-UP publications had received more than three times as many citations per year as a typical (median) NIH-funded publication from the same field and publication year. Similarly, the median RCR score for the RADx-UP publications is 3.00. This indicates that the accrual of citations per year for the median RADx-UP paper is three times that of a typical (median) NIH-funded publication in the same field and publication year. These RCR measures are subject to change as more publications in this data set receive RCR values as citations accrue over time. At the same time, the initial RCR data indicate the RADx-UP publications have a greater-than-typical citation rate compared to NIH-funded papers in the same field and year. This citation-based metric in turn indicates greater-than-typical scientific influence of these publications, compared to that of the NIH-funded paper cohort.

Table 3: Relative Citation Ratio Data (as of March 31, 2023)

Relative Citation Ratio (RCR) Data	Value
Number of 70 RADx-UP publications with assigned RCR values	65 (of 194) publications
Average (Mean) RCR	3.17
Median RCR	3.00
Maximum RCR	11.00
Minimum RCR	0.00

PlumX Metrics

Understanding how often RADx-UP work is mentioned in news, social media, and policy documents can indicate the knowledge advancement beyond scholarly communities. We used PlumX metrics tool integrated with Scopus to capture six altmetric measures. Out of 196 RADx-UP publications, 194 had PlumX Metrics associated with them. See **Figure 4** for the metrics with counts of altmetric indicators for these 194 publications.

² Relative Citation Ratio is not available for papers published last fiscal year, since, in general, not enough time has passed for citation statistics to meaningfully accrue in that period. An exception is made for papers with 5 or more citations since publication, as these are deemed to be accruing citations quickly enough for reliable calculations. The current year in the database increments with the NIH Fiscal Year every October. For example, in June 2019 (NIH Fiscal Year 2019), papers from 2018 receive provisional RCRs if they have 5 citations or more, and all papers from 2017 receive provisional RCRs. In October 2019 (the start of NIH Fiscal Year 2020), papers from 2019 receive provisional RCRs if they have 5 citations or more, and all papers from 2018 receive provisional RCRs (National Institutes of Health Office of Portfolio Analysis, n.d.).

Policy Exploration

A more detailed exploration of the policy documents citing RADx-UP scholarly work was conducted. Policy documents citing RADx-UP publications can indicate an explicit translation from research to public decision-making.

In addition to the policy impact articles that we reported in 2022, there are six new policy citations so far in 2023 and 14 in total. Policy citations indicate that local, national, or global institutions are using RADx-UP research to understand or advocate for COVID-19 testing and vaccinations in underserved populations. The US Department of Health and Human Services cites Hendricks et al. 2021 extensively to demonstrate the connection between socioeconomic status and COVID-19 outcomes in a report about the data collection on socioeconomic status and disease. The World Bank cites Berry et al. 2021 as evidence for the importance of tailoring communication strategies to healthcare workers in a report on strengthening healthcare systems during the pandemic. Similarly, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) cites Konetzka et al. 2021 in showing that adequately staffed long-term care facilities have more COVID-19 cases but overall lower mortality in a book on health system resilience. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention cites Bardenheier et al. 2021 as evidence that the COVID-19 vaccine does not have an impact on 7-day mortality in older adults in a presentation on vaccine safety. These four policy translations increase the impact of RADx-UP articles beyond the research community.

Discussion & Conclusions

This second bibliographic analysis of the growing set of research publications produced by the RADx-UP Program focuses on assessing indicators of the program's research performance at the approximately one-year mark since the initial analysis. We used traditional bibliometric measures (e.g., publication and citation counts); the newer field- and time-normalized Relative Citation Ratio (RCR) measure developed by the NIH Office of Portfolio Analysis and available via iCite; and PlumX altmetric data via Scopus to assess RADx-UP scholarly articles published from 2020 into 2023 that Scopus had indexed as of March 31, 2023. Given the larger though still modest publication set (i.e., 196 publications) and the 3 or fewer years since publication, this analysis provides an indication of the RADx-UP Program's evolving research productivity and influence, as well as of public engagement with the research, demonstrated by PlumX data.

Based on the bibliometric measures outlined in this report, the RADx-UP Program shows continuing signs of strong productivity, influence, and public engagement with the research.

- Research productivity as measured by scholarly publication output per year indicates a substantial upward trend, supported at least in part by the growth in the number of RADx-UP research projects from 69 in 2020 to 125 as of March 31, 2023. One article published in 2020 grew to 41³ articles

³ The Bibliometrics Report from November 2022 identified 44 articles published in 2021. The publication year for an article in PubMed and Scopus can change over time as pre-print articles are ultimately published. A RADx-UP Project may also later reject a publication linked to their project when completing the quarterly Scholarly & Non-Scholarly Product Survey. Both cases may lead to inconsistencies in publications data over time.

published in 2021, 119 articles published in 2022, and 28 articles published within the first 3 months of 2023. Publications from 2023 are on pace to approximate 2022 output by the end of the year.

- Research influence as indicated by citations counts is also notable. Citation count data were available from Scopus for 189 articles of the 196 total RADx-UP scholarly publications. Those 189 articles had a combined total of 966 citations (self-citations included) that had accrued since the articles' publication. Thirteen articles published in 2021 had received 20 or more citations each. Four of these articles (Berry et al., 2021; Carlsten et al., 2021; Harrison et al., 2021; and Klonoff et al., 2021;) had received 40 or more citations each, indicating significant influence in the research community in the two years since publication.
- Research influence as measured by time- and field- normalized RCR scores indicate the RADx-UP publications have a greater-than-typical citation rate compared to NIH-funded papers in the same field and year. This in, turn, indicates greater-than-typical scientific influence of these publications, compared to that benchmark group of papers.
- Public engagement, as indicated by PlumX altmetric data, indicates significant engagement with RADx-UP publications. Most notably in terms of impact, 10 policy documents have cited RADx-UP articles 14 times. State and national policymakers are including RADx-UP findings in disseminations to the public and scientific audiences. Additionally, organizations and institutions are using RADx-UP findings to highlight factors that strengthen health system responses to the pandemic for underserved communities.

Through the bibliometrics analysis, we can understand how the RADx-UP Program meets the evaluation objectives of **Understanding of the Social, Ethical, and Behavioral Implications (SEBI) of COVID-19 testing and vaccination in target population** and **Critical knowledge advancement to address COVID-19 disparities**. In this second year of bibliometrics reporting, the RCR scores continue to show strong uptake of RADx-UP publications in scholarly communities, improving our understanding of COVID-19 testing and vaccination among underserved populations. Combining publication content analysis data with bibliometric data shows that RADx-UP publications are improving the understanding of testing and vaccination in most target populations funded through the grant. Altmetric data like mentions and citations in news, social media, and policy also indicate that RADx-UP findings are translating beyond scholarly communities. Policy citations in particular demonstrate that the social, ethical, and behavioral implications of COVID-19 testing and vaccination from the RADx-UP Program are relevant for government decision-making.

Recommendations & Implications

1. **Maximize research productivity by addressing research publication gaps.**
There is a substantial increase in the number of RADx-UP publications and citation impacts. However, papers focused on under-represented populations (sexual and gender minority, research from US territories) and those using evidence-based methodological approaches (cost-benefit papers and experimental and experimental approaches) are fewer than desired in a program focused on assessing the effectiveness of COVID-19 testing strategies. Researchers should focus on publishing more studies within these identified areas.
2. **Publish data on evidence-based impacts:** More methodologically rigorous research publications on COVID-19 testing and vaccination cost-effectiveness, cost savings and policy/legislative impacts are needed to continually advance RADx-UP scientific contributions. The increasing number of policy citations indicates that RADx-UP research is informing public decision-making. Researchers should aim to further bridge the gap between research and

policy, ensuring that their findings directly contribute to evidence-based policy recommendations.

3. **Explicitly describe community outreach and engagement strategies:** The prevalence of partnerships with Community-Based Organizations (CBOs) as an engagement strategy underscores the importance of community involvement in research initiatives. However, there is need for more publications that explicitly describe their engagement and outreach processes as well as the benefits of utilizing multiple community engagement strategies in order to build sustainable community-academic partnerships that works even after project close-out.

Limitations

1. **Early Stage of Scholarly Production:** This second year of analysis provides baseline signals about research productivity, influence and engagement. However, the analysis and resulting assessment is limited by the absence of citation data that take time to accrue and RCR values that not available for publications from the prior NIH fiscal year.² As the body of research outputs continues to grow and those outputs have time to accrue citation-based measures (e.g., citation counts and RCR values), future bibliometric analyses will have an increasing amount of measures data available to assess program's research performance more clearly.
2. **Measures Not Included:** This year's analysis, like last year's, utilizes citation counts from Scopus and RCR values from NIH iCite. Other measures assigned to Scopus publications such as Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) and Citation Benchmarking (CB) are not practically retrievable for citation sets without a companion subscription to Elsevier's SciVal product. No primary RADx-UP institutions maintain institutional access to this tool and these metrics.

Next Steps

For the final RADx-UP Bibliometric analysis in 2025, we plan to leverage a newly acquired subscription to Dimensions to obtain both RCR values and Dimension's Field Citation (FCR)³ values for RADx-UP publications in addition to citation counts for the RADx-UP publication set. The FCR will provide an additional field- and time- normalized citation measure to complement the RCR from NIH.

For Dimension's FCR, the field to which publications are compared is defined by the Field of Research classifications automatically assigned to all two or more-year-old Dimensions articles by machine learning processes. For NIH's RCR, which is only assigned to all two or more year-old NIH-funded research papers indexed in PubMed, the field is defined by the set of articles a given article is cited alongside i.e. its co-citation network. These two different comparative citation indicators will provide additional data on which to base assessments of citation impact or influence of RADx-UP publications.